

HYPERLIPIDEMIA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT STRATEGIES AND MANAGEMENT APPROACHES

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Abstract

Background: High cholesterol and HDL levels, or hyperlipidemia, raise the risk of cardiovascular disease, particularly in people between the ages of 40 and 75 who also have comorbid diseases or consume a lot of fat. Cardiovascular disease and atherosclerosis are brought on by high lipid levels.

Objective: Investigating the various symptoms, diagnosis, and modern treatment options for hyperlipidemia is the aim of this comprehensive analysis. It will specifically look at how novel therapeutic medications, such as PCSK9 inhibitors, work and emphasize how important lifestyle modifications are to both treating and preventing this disease.

Methodology: This review looks at the pathogenesis, etiology, epidemiology, diagnosis, and therapeutic management of hyperlipidemia. It focuses on various lipoprotein types, lipid metabolism mechanisms, measurement methods, risk assessment, medication therapies, and lifestyle changes.

Conclusion: Hyperlipidemia is a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases that requires lifestyle modifications and early detection. Pharmacological therapy, such as PCSK9 inhibitors and statins, which target environmental factors, genetic predispositions, and LDLc lowering, should be used as part of treatment to prevent major health problems

INTRODUCTION

Hyperlipidemia, which increases lipid levels, is the cause of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease. Ischemic heart disease, which is caused by narrowing blood arteries and leads to peripheral vascular disorders, heart attacks, and coronary cerebrovascular disease, is the third leading cause of death globally. ⁽¹⁾ Lipids are lipoproteins VLDL, Apo lipoproteins, LDL and HDL. ⁽²⁾ Another main cause of Hyperlipidemia is liver injury. Liver maintain or control blood cholesterol level in body. About 80% cholesterol in body. ⁽³⁾

Lipoproteins

Lipoproteins, which are macro nucleated proteins and lipids influenced by dietary factors like high blood lipid levels, saturated fat, and cholesterol, can cause elevated blood pressure and heart attacks. ⁽⁴⁾ Lipoprotein is one of the major causes of Hyperlipidemia. There are 3 types of lipoproteins i.e. 1) LDL 2) HDL and 3) VDL (Very low density Lipoproteins) ⁽⁵⁾ LDL is also called bad protein increase in level of LDL leads to development of atherosclerotic plaque & vascular disease. HDL regulates cholesterol level decrease level of HDL leads to CVDS. In treatment of CVDDS we decrease LDL & also manage risk factors responsible for Hyperlipidemia disease.

Figure 1 shows that triglyceride-rich lipoprotein VLDL is composed of phospholipid membrane, cholesterol ester, TG, and Apo A, B-100, and C. It is secreted by the colon and transformed into CM residual by lipoprotein lipase (LPL). Both VLDL and VLDL residual bind to the VLDL receptor.⁽⁶⁾

Mechanisms of Health and Disease

Inflammation and Atherogenesis: By promoting the formation of plaque and inflammation in arteries, LDL and Lp(a) raise the risk of cardiovascular disease. HDL helps remove cholesterol from tissues and has anti-inflammatory properties.⁽⁷⁻⁹⁾

Genetic Factors: Between 70 and 90 percent of Lp(a) levels are genetically determined; this range varies significantly among populations, with some ethnic groups and postmenopausal women having higher levels.^(10, 11)

Methods of Measurement, Risk, and Therapy Evaluation

Accurate measurement of lipoproteins: Especially Lp(a), is essential for risk classification. Standardization of assays remains challenging.⁽¹²⁻¹⁴⁾

Treatments: Conventional lipid-lowering drugs have no discernible effect on Lp (a). The effects of novel RNA-based therapies on cardiovascular outcomes are still being studied, but they seem to have the potential to significantly reduce Lp(a) levels.^(15, 16) Nowadays level of LDL increase among people which show that continuous positive correlation between LDL & CVDS.⁽¹⁷⁾ Many diseases like myocardial infarction occur due to blood clotting in blood vessels which lead to heart attack or myocardial infarction.⁽¹⁸⁾

Lipoprotein Function

Lipoprotein perform many functions in body such as it imparts in lipid solubilization to transport triglyceride as it important source of energy. It transport fatty acid, cholesterol, triglyceride to various body organs & act as source of energy by metabolism of fats.⁽¹⁹⁾

Etiology

Hyperlipidemia classified into two subclasses.

1. Primary genetic
2. A Secondary (Acquired)

1. Primary

Occurred from birth means genetic disorder & secondary which is acquired due to diet, environment, comorbidity i.e. diabetes, lifestyle, hormonal imbalance, liver disorder & decreased body exercise, or healthy foods. Primary Hyperlipidemia due to distraction in metabolism of LDL about 50% coronary artery disease ue to heredity disorder.⁽²⁰⁾

2. Secondary

Secondary Hyperlipidemia causes are obesity, unhealthy food and many other factors lead to CADs.

Excessive intake of fat or diet, this fat deposit in blood vessels and arteries narrow those leads to stroke, IHD & heart failure. Other factors include the risk of above disease like diabetes, age renal failure & hormonal imbalance & excessive use of

drugs like beta blockers, estrogen, progesterone contraceptive etc.⁽²¹⁾

Epidemiology

Hyperlipidemia is a chronic disease which spread among people speedy about three million people of United States of Europe suffered from Hyperlipidemia. Many versions of which

Hyperlipidemia disease increase like bad LDL, life style, liver injury and age. In male age 55 to 60 years' risk of CADs more because of Hyperlipidemia. Approximately, about 50% American adults have LDL elevated & 35% of those people manage their LDL level prevalence of dyslipidemia greater among white than black.⁽²²⁾

Table 01 shows that according to the data, white adults and men are more likely than black adults and women to have dyslipidemia.

White	Black
Women 64.1%	Women 49.5%
Men 78.4%	Men 56.7%

P < 0.001 for both & among men than women P ≤ 0.02 ethical groups.

In such countries where consumption of saturated fat is low & rate of obesity is decreasing, chances of Hyperlipidemia is less.

Children under age of two years, underweight, or obese, may develop secondary pediatric Hyperlipidemia.⁽¹⁾

Pathology

Hyperlipidemia mainly LDL is the major risk factor of CAD, IHD, the stroke. In blood increased saturated fats, which is not easily metabolized & move freely deposited in the vessels narrow them, distribution in blood flow leads to stroke, IHD & CVDs. Other factors like inflammatory & immunological factors, hypertension, diabetics, liver disorder smoking cause CVD & IHD.

Atherosclerosis occurs due to damage of endothelial lining leads to inflammatory dysfunction & accumulation of lipids & this lipid develop from cell by engulfing of macrophages. Now cholesterol deposit in from cell cause apoptosis, necrosis of cell or tissue. In smooth muscles the form cell fibrotic plaque inhibits lipid metabolism & tissue being destroyed.

Due to inflammation or damage on tissue increase platelet ratio leads to coagulation causes thrombosis. In case any injure tissue factors release increase platelets activity, coagulation & thrombosis plaque occur which deposited into blood vessels leads to thromboembolic pulmonary diseases.⁽²³⁾

Many cases Hyperlipidemia occurs due to secondary factor like manifestation, obesity, saturated fat intake high content of cholesterol in diet.

Another reason of Hyperlipidemia apo B-100 Lipoproteins in plasma which leads to atherosclerosis disease. Other factors include environmental factors, smoking, genetic disorder, these all above major risks of CVDs, IHD.

Many disease which is due to Hyperlipidemia or dyslipidemia & atherosclerotic problems include; Crohn's disease, Chronic pain, Depression, Chronic Kidney disease, inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) etc.⁽²⁴⁾

Histopathology

Due to Hyperlipidemia intrinsic attraction & shear velocities of patellar tendon negatively involved, not only vascular structure changed because of hyper in presence of Hyperlipidemia. The shear velocities are also changed. The microbiological structure of tissue tendon change they are stiffer; fiber is damaged collagen cell replaced by lipid cell may be due to change in collagen type which are cell elastic. Hyperlipidemia cause tendon injury, tendon are less elastic effect & more susceptible for damage⁽²⁵⁾.

Mechanism of Action

Drugs function as structural mimics of HMG-coenzyme A reductase, preventing the liver from producing cholesterol. Along with the reduction of total cholesterol in plasma, triglyceride, LDL, and HDL levels are also decreased. Diallylsulfide and

diallylthiosulfide compounds, which are also inhibitors of HMG coenzyme A reductase, reduce cholesterol production by 10-25% at low concentrations.⁽²⁶⁾

By blocking the liver's cholesterol-producing enzyme, statins and other HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors lower cholesterol.⁽²⁷⁾ There is also a continuous search for new inhibitors with improved effects.⁽²⁸⁾

Mechanism and Effects

Statins: Because statins inhibit HMG-CoA reductase, which reduces the liver's production of cholesterol and lowers LDL and plasma cholesterol levels, they

can help treat hypercholesterolemia and prevent cardiovascular disease.^(29, 30)

Novel strategies: that may be able to overcome statin-induced enzyme buildup and enhance the effects of cholesterol-lowering drugs include compounds that both block and promote the breakdown of the enzyme.^(27, 31, 32)

Types of Lipoprotein

Lipoproteins consist of three types:⁽³³⁾

1. LDL
2. HDL
3. VLDL

Figure 2 shows that the body contains several types of lipoproteins, including chylomicrons, VLDL, IDL, LDL, and HDL.

Low Density Lipoproteins (LDL)

LDL is also called “bad cholesterol” because it can cause heart attack, stroke etc. It contain high quantity of cholesterol which leads to plaque, arteries become narrow & decreased blood flow results in Myocardial infarction.⁽¹⁷⁾

High Density Lipoproteins (HDL)

HDL contains low quantity of cholesterol, no cause any plaque & resistance in blood flow. Prevent from Heart diseases.⁽³⁴⁾

Very Low Density Lipoproteins (VLDL)

VLDL → relative density of extracellular water that enables fats & cholesterol to move within the water based solution of blood stream. Now we can calculate total cholesterol by sum of HDL, LDL and triglycerides. If score is “high”, It is an indication of heart disease, a health cholesterol ranges for you depend on your age, family history, life style and risk factors.⁽³⁵⁾

Table 1 effect of cholesterol.⁽³⁶⁾

Total Cholesterol Level	Category
Less than 200 mg/dl	Desirable
200-239	Borderline (high)
240 mg/dl and above	High

Insulin found in adipose tissue which activates lipoprotein lipase. Almost dietary fats are from intestinal lumen into intestinal lymph and finally reached to chylomicrons. Now it's more into bloodstream.

Types of Hyperlipidemia

The following types of hyperlipidemia which have different effect on blood.⁽³⁷⁾

Type-I

Hyperlipidemia classification

Table about hyperlipidemia classification.^(20, 21)

Primary	Secondary
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familial (genetic disorder) also called monogenic (single gene) defect or polygenic • Occurred due to abnormal lipoproteins • Familial defective apolipoprotein B100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquired • caused by: diabetes, Chronic alcoholism, Nephritic Hypothyroidism, Use of corticosterone, Beta blockers, antipsychotics, retinoic acid and diuretics etc, HIV, Pcos and renal disease

Causes

Cholesterol; trans-fat, saturated fat; these all increase lipid level in blood.

Ice cream, meat, dairy products, cheese, egg yolk etc.⁽⁴⁵⁾

Other causes

Obesity, smoking, drug abuse, metabolic syndrome, pregnancy, sedentary life style, excessive consumption of alcohol etc.⁽⁴⁶⁾

Symptoms

Lead to atherosclerosis, angina, heart attack or stroke.⁽⁴⁷⁾

Level of fats increase and deposit fat below eye especially.⁽⁴⁸⁾

Swollen by liver & pancreas.⁽⁴⁹⁾

Mostly occur in children⁽³⁸⁾. It can cause pancreas infection & enlargement of liver and abdominal pain. Hereditary disorder also known as LPL deficiency (destruction of fat)^(39, 40)

Type-II

Normally deposit around eye, also known as high level of LDL.⁽⁴¹⁾

Type-III

Known as low (LDL) & high (HDL) effect level of lipoprotein cause yellowish plaque around eyes. It is a symptom of cardiovascular disease.⁽⁴²⁾

Type-IV:

Decreased cholesterol tends, increase triglycerides level, which directly leads to obesity.⁽⁴³⁾

But these can be controlled through diet.⁽⁴⁴⁾

Vessels blocked.⁽⁵⁰⁾

Diagnosis

- Regular checkup of fat (LDL, HDL, VLDL & Triglycerides through blood test)
- Blood test called lipid panel or lipid profile
- Fasting test, this means that a person should refrain from eating or drinking anything for 9-12 hours before test.⁽⁵¹⁾

Treatment

Changes in life style

Poor diet (balanced diet), less weight of body, regular exercise, having non-oily food, have fish (two times in a week).⁽⁵²⁾

The figure no 3 shows how bile acid sequestrants work, producing an insoluble substance that stops bile acid reabsorption in patients receiving treatment and causing bile acid reabsorption in hyper lipidemic patients who are not receiving treatment.

Therapeutic Management

Drugs

1. Statins: Mechanism: prevent gluteryl coenzyme reductase

Lovastatin (10-80 mg)

Simvastatin (5-40 mg)

Atorvastatin (10-80 mg)

Rosuvastatin (5-20 mg)

Statins avert smooth muscles cell & obstruct the stimulation of tumor necrosis factor.

Effects

3-hydroxy-3-methyl

Increase HDDL & decrease LDL and TG

Drugs

2. Bile Acid Binding Resins:

Cholestyramine (4-16 mg)

Colestipol (5-30 mg)

Effects

Decrease LDL

Increase HDL

No effect on TG

Drugs

3. Fibric Acid Derivatives:

Gemifibrozil (1200 mg)

Bezafibrate (600 mg)

Fenofibrate (200 mg)

Effects

Decrease TG & LDL

Increase HDL

Figure no 4 shows that the gemfibrozil is a fibrate that increases lipoprotein lipase activity, which releases free fatty acids for tissues and reduces the amount of VLDL and IDL that remains in capillaries.

Drugs

4. Nicotinic Acid Derivatives:

5. Niacin (2-6 gm)

Effects

Decrease TG & LDL

Increase HDL

Drugs

6. Cholesterol Absorption Inhibitor:

7. Ezetimibe (10 mg)

Effects

Decrease LDL

Decrease cholesterol.^(21, 53)

Complications

Untreated Hyperlipidemia includes lead to all vascular disease, peripheral artery disease, type-II diabetes, high B.P and even death.^(54, 55)

Prevention

Life style, dietary option, regular exercise, low cheesy food, low intake of alcohol, omega-3-oil which contains unsaturated fats.^(52, 56)

Side Effects

Statins can cause GI symptoms also headache myalgia and dizziness

Statins can cause myopathy, rhabdomyosis, increase serum transaminase, which is harmful for kidney, Also cause Cardiomyopathy, renal and type-II diabetes.⁽⁵⁷⁾

Future Directions

Future research should focus on treating hyperlipidemia in a customized way, accounting for genetic predispositions and treatments, investigating the long-term effects of new drugs, and understanding how lifestyle modifications impact lipid metabolism and cardiovascular health.

Methodology

Data collection: As part of the literature review's data collection process, peer-reviewed articles were methodically located and evaluated. The publications were found using the following keywords: Hyperlipidemia, Cholesterol, Triglycerides, LDL, HDL, Cardiovascular Disease, Diagnosis, Treatment, Lifestyle.

Article Selection: We selected articles from the PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases. Depending on their applicability, systemic reviews, clinical trials, meta-analyses, and cohort studies were considered for Diagnosis, Treatment Strategies and Management Approaches for hyperlipidemia. Only English-language works published in indexed journals between 2015 and 2025 were included in the selection process, with an emphasis on subjects like Diagnosis, Treatment Strategies and Management Approaches of Hyperlipidemia.

Discussion

This review covers in detail the causes, prevalence, and pathological consequences of hyperlipidemia, a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, as well as the critical roles that "good" HDL and "bad" LDL play in its development. Although genetic factors can play a role, lifestyle choices like diet and inactivity are the main causes of secondary hyperlipidemia, which is prevalent worldwide. The disease's complex pathophysiology includes endothelial damage and inflammation, which impact not only the arteries' health but also that of other organ systems. Current management strategies combine pharmacological interventions, primarily statins, with other lipid-lowering drugs and more recent medications, like PCSK9 inhibitors, with significant lifestyle modifications, like diet, exercise, and weight control, to reduce LDL-c more effectively. Despite these advancements, problems like patient adherence and side effect management persist, underscoring the need for customized treatment regimens that integrate lifestyle and medication strategies with genetic information to optimize patient outcomes.

Conclusion

The pharmaceutical manufacturing sector is undergoing a profound and long-lasting revolution driven by innovation and shifting regulatory requirements. The development of adaptable regulatory pathways for Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMPs) and the application of Continuous Manufacturing (CM) to boost output and quality are two examples of this shift. The strategic integration of Process Analytical Technology (PAT) and Quality by Design (QbD), which

revolutionizes drug development and enables real-time quality control, is primarily responsible for these advancements. To overcome significant challenges like high investment and complexity, interdisciplinary collaboration must still be prioritized, skilled personnel must be hired, digital solutions (like digital twins and artificial intelligence) must be adopted, and global regulatory harmonization must be encouraged. The sector can ensure that safer, more efficient, and more accessible medicines globally.

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There is no conflict of interest among authors.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Chat GPT to enhance the readability of the article. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and took(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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